

Synthetic, spectral and antibacterial studies of some novel first transition metal complexes of 4,6-diamino-1,3,5-triazine-2-thiol

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A series of complexes of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{III}, VO^{II} and Zn^{II} with the *s*-triazine, 4,6-diamino-1,3,5-triazine-2-thiol known as thioammeline (HTA) and its sodium salt (NaTA) have been prepared and characterized through elemental analyses, magnetic moment measurements, electronic, IR and ESR spectroscopic techniques. The complexes were found to be neutral and both HTA and NaTA coordinate to the metal ion as anion TA⁻ in the thiol form to give identical complexes for each metal ion. The electrochemical behaviour of the complexes was explored using cyclic voltammetry and it is seen that the metal-ligand linkage has high covalent nature. The Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes are square-planar, Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes are tetrahedral, VO^{II} complex is square pyramidal and Fe^{III} complex is octahedral. The copper complex has a tetragonal unit cell with $a = b = 12.6 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 10.1 \text{ \AA}$. HTA, NaTA and the complexes were screened for their antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*.

1,3,5-Triazines (*sym*-triazines or *s*-triazines) are among the earliest recognized organic compounds, the derivatives of which are used in the field of agriculture, medicine and industry¹. The most convenient reported method for the preparation of 4,6-diamino-1,3,5-triazine-2-thiol is by the reaction between dicyandiamide and thiourea in acid medium^{2,3}. The coordination chemistry of triazines is less extensive except for a few reports⁴⁻⁶. In the present paper the synthesis, characterisation and antistaphylococcal activity of the complexes of 4,6-diamino-1,3,5-triazine-2-thiol (HTA) and its sodium salt (NaTA) with the transition metal ions Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Fe^{III}, VO^{II}, Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} are described.

Results and discussion

The complexes synthesized for each metal with HTA and NaTA were found identical in their properties such as colour, decomposition temperature and analytical data. They also have the same spectral and magnetic properties. These reveal that HTA and NaTA are identical in their coordination behaviour. The structure of the ligands HTA and NaTA are represented in Fig. 1.

The complexes reported here are stable and decompose only above 210°. The metal analyses data show that in the complexes of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II}, Zn^{II} and VO^{II}, the metal-

Fig. 1

ligand ratio is 1 : 2 whereas for the iron complex it is 1 : 3. The results are presented in Table 1.

Infrared spectra : The ligand bands at 3420 and 3218 cm⁻¹ assigned to the symmetric and asymmetric stretching of the NH₂ groups have undergone downward shift by 20 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. This indicates the coordination of amino N to metal ion^{7,8}. The weak band around 2400 cm⁻¹ and another strong one at 1235 cm⁻¹ in HTA, which is absent in NaTA and also in complexes can be assigned to the vibrations of the S-H group⁸. Thus it may be inferred that complexation takes place through the thiol sulphur after deprotonation.

The bands around 1680, 1650, 1540 and 1490 cm⁻¹ due to exocyclic C=N bond, N-C-N stretching, N-H bending and endocyclic C=N group vibrations, respectively, of both HTA and NaTA do not suffer any change in the complexes⁹. The weak band at 1080 cm⁻¹ ($\nu_{C=S}$) is present only in HTA

Table 1. Metal percentage, colour, decomposition temperature, magnetic moment and CV peaks of the complexes

Complex (Colour)	Decom. temp.	Metal% (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} (B.M.) at RT	CV peaks (mV)
Cu(TA) ₂ (Yellow)	210	18.32 (18.28)	1.81	135 and 413
Ni(TA) ₂ (Green)	275	17.20 (17.12)	3.37	12 and 638
Co(TA) ₂ (Purple)	264	17.20 (17.18)	3.62	-97 and 416
Mn(TA) ₂ (Violet)	227	16.32 (16.20)	5.44	-541 and 217
Zn(TA) ₂ (White)	219	18.75 (18.71)	Diamag.	Not studied
VO(TA) ₂ (Green)	232	14.56 (14.50)	1.77	72 and 112
Fe(TA) ₃ (Yellow)	258	11.68 (11.59)	5.71	Not studied

due to its tautomeric thione form⁷. But its absence in the sodium salt and complexes confirm that the complexes are formed in the thiol form after deprotonation. The medium non-ligand bands around 470 and 390 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ vibrations¹⁰. These indicate the coordination through S atom of deprotonated thiol and N atom at the 4 or 6 positions which are identical. The involvement of thiol sulphur after deprotonation can be further confirmed by the disappearance of HTA band at 2400 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu_{\text{S-H}}$ and the upward shift of $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ band by 10 cm⁻¹.

Electrical conductance: The complexes are soluble only in DMSO and DMF and these solutions are non-conducting which indicates that the complexes are non-electrolytes.

Magnetic moments: The measured μ_{eff} values (Table 1) of the complexes are in agreement with the spin only value for respective metal ions. Ni(TA)₂ is diamagnetic for square-planar geometry. Co(TA)₂ shows μ_{eff} very close to the spin only value expected for tetrahedral complexes¹¹. The slightly lower value for μ_{eff} exhibited by Fe(TA)₃ complex than the spin only value expected for high spin octahedral complexes may be due to metal-metal interaction¹².

Electronic spectra: Cu(TA)₂ exhibits a strong absorption band at 860 nm for the three overlapping ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions characteristic of D_{4h} symmetry¹³. The band at 610 nm and the shoulder at 430 nm shown by Ni(TA)₂ are characteristic transitions ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{2g}$ of square-planar complex¹⁴. Co(TA)₂ shows an absorption at 650 nm which can be attributed to ${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ transition of tetrahedral complexes¹⁵. Along with the MLCT of Mn(TA)₂ at 410 nm

which is responsible for its violet colour, the band obtained at 690 nm can be attributed to the transition from the sextet ground state to the first excited quartet state¹⁶. The electronic absorption bands shown by VO(TA)₂ around 440 and 480 nm can be attributed to CT mixed with $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}$, d_{yz} transitions for VO^{II} complexes with D_{4h} symmetry¹⁷. The weak absorption bands around 500 nm shown by Fe(TA)₃ are due to spin forbidden transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$, respectively, found to occur in octahedral Fe^{III} complexes¹⁸.

Cyclic voltammetry: The CV profile of the complex was studied in deaerated DMSO solution with a three electrode system consisting of Ag/AgCl, KCl reference electrode, Pt auxiliary electrode and glassy carbon working electrode. A scan rate of 100 mV/s was used. Only quasi-reversible peaks are seen in the case of these complexes. So it can be assumed that the metal-sulphur linkage in the complexes is predominantly covalent in nature^{19,20}.

ESR spectra: The polycrystalline ESR spectrum of VO(TA)₂ at RT was recorded at a microwave frequency of 9.22 GHz and field set of 2500 G. Hyperfine splitting with partial overlap is seen both in the perpendicular and parallel components. The g and A values calculated are $g_{\parallel} = 1.9290$, $g_{\perp} = 1.9777$, $g_{\text{av}} = 1.9614$, $A_{\parallel} = 171$ G and $A_{\perp} = 100$ G. These values match that of a VO²⁺ ion in axial symmetry. $g_{\parallel} < g_{\perp} < g_e$ is the consequence of the unpaired electron in the d_{xy} orbital of the VO²⁺ ion²¹.

X-Ray analysis of the complex: The X-ray powder diffraction pattern of the complex Cu(TA)₂ was taken to examine whether the complex is crystalline and if so to determine the nature and size of the unit cell. The range of 2θ was from 5–45°. Forty reflections were obtained in this region and sixteen reflections were successfully indexed. Indexing was done by a trial and error method. It is seen that the tetragonal system gave the best fit²². The sample is found to have a tetragonal unit cell with the cell edges as $a = b = 12.6$ Å and $c = 10.1$ Å. The volume of the unit cell is 1603.476 Å³.

Antibacterial activity: HTA, NaTA and all the complexes were screened for their antistaphylococcal activity by administering them at a concentration of 0.05 mg ml⁻¹ in a homogeneous liquid culture medium containing *S. aureus* and assayed by turbidimetric method²³. The complexes were found to exhibit more antistaphylococcal activity than HTA and NaTA. Among the complexes, Zn(TA)₂ showed the highest activity.

Based on the above data and discussion, the ligand 4,6-

diamino-1,3,5-triazine-2-thiol and its sodium salt act as monoanionic bidentate coordinating through its amino nitrogen at the 4 or 6 position and the thiol sulphur atom. The analytical, magnetic and spectral data indicate that the complexes formed by HTA and NaTA with a metal are identical in all respects. The electronic spectra and magnetic moment data reveal that, the copper complex has a square-planar geometry, nickel, cobalt, manganese and zinc complexes have a tetrahedral geometry. Similarly, an octahedral geometry for iron and a square-pyramidal geometry for the vanadyl complexes can be recommended.

Experimental

Preparation of the sodium salt of thioammeline : Thioammeline (4,6-diamino-1,3,5-triazine-2-thiol) was prepared by the reported method². The sodium salt of thioammeline was prepared by the following method. Finely powdered thioammeline (2.86 g, 0.02 mol) was added to 20 ml of 1 M NaOH solution and stirred well. The salt formed dissolved and was regenerated by slow evaporation. The sodium salt was purified by recrystallisation from water. Yield, 3.1 g (95%).

General method for the preparation of a thioammeline complexes : Finely powdered thioammeline (1.43 g, 0.01 mol) was dissolved in 100 ml DMF or the sodium salt of thioammeline (1.65 g, 0.01 mol) in 50 ml water at water bath temperature. To this was added an aqueous solution (50 ml) of the metal salt (0.006 mol). In the case of the iron complex 50 ml of aqueous $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.09 g, 0.004 mol) was used. Immediate precipitation of the complexes occurred. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for half an hour and filtered. The complexes were washed repeatedly with distilled water and dried.

The metal salts used for complex synthesis were $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Analyses and measurements : C, H and N analyses of the samples were done by the microanalytical technique at the Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, North Eastern Hill University, Shillong, India. Metal and sulfur were determined gravimetrically and the metal percentage was confirmed by atomic absorption spectroscopy at the Geological Survey of India Laboratory, Trivandrum. Conductance measurements were carried out on a digital, Control Dynamics (APX 185) conductivity meter. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made using a Gouy balance at RT using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ as calibrant. The electronic spec-

tra of the ligands and complexes in DMF were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-1601 spectrophotometer. The IR spectra of the ligands and complexes were taken on a Perkin-Elmer RXI FT IR spectrophotometer using KBr discs. Cyclic voltammetric studies of a few complexes were done in de-aerated DMSO solution on a Cypress systems model CS-1090/CS-1087 computer controlled electroanalytical system. The X-band ESR spectra of the complex $\text{VO}(\text{TA})_2$ (polycrystalline) were recorded at RT on a Jeol JM FE3 X-band spectrometer. The powder X-ray diffraction pattern of $\text{Cu}(\text{TA})_2$ was recorded on a Philips analytical PW 1710 X-ray diffractometer using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ (40 kV, 20 mA) X-ray of wavelength 1.54060 Å.

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